

RETROSPECTIVE STUDIES ON PREVALENCE OF MALARIA IN PATIENTS FROM FOUR TOWNS OF KADUNA STATE, NIGERIA. (2013 – 2017)

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ABSTRACT

Malaria disease has been reported to be associated with five different Plasmodium species. Plasmodium falciparum is the most virulent of the species. In West Africa and in Nigeria, malaria is a public health disease affecting both children and adults. This research was designed to carry out a retrospective studies the prevalence of Malaria, from four health centers in Kaduna State. In addition, the prevalence of malaria with respect to age range and gender were also studied. The total malaria patient attendance for the period of 2013 to 2017 from Kachia, Kafanchan, Kaduna and Zaria towns were studied. Ethical Permission was obtained from Kaduna State Ministry of health. Observation from the results of the retrospective studies showed that the total reported Patient attendance (%) from four towns in Kaduna State from 2013 to 2017 was shown to be one hundred and fifty six thousand and fifty three (156,053). The average (mean) patient attendance from four towns in Kaduna State from 2013 to 2017 was twenty six thousand and nine (26,009). The total number of reported malaria patients attendance from four different health facilities in the four towns in Kaduna State Nigeria (2013 to 2017) was thirty four thousand, one hundred and twenty one (34,121). The percentage prevalence of Malaria in Kaduna State from the four health centers in these towns (Kaduna, Kafanchan, Kachia, Zaria), from 2013 to 2017 was 21.87%. The reported percentage prevalence of malaria cases from patients in each of the four health centers studied in Kaduna, Kafanchan, Zaria, and Kachia from 2013 to 2017 was 24.74%, 28.22%, 18.51%, and 28.39% .respectively. The yearly reported malaria cases showed that Kafanchan and Kachia towns had the highest prevalence rate of 28.22% and 28.39% respectively. This higher prevalence of malaria seen in the southern senatorial towns agrees with the work of Garba et al., (2016) who was of the opinion that the reason was due to higher rainfall of 1530mm. Malaria was more prevalent during the rainy seasons than in the dry season. It was also observed that the malaria prevalence rate reportedly was higher in females (21.87%) than in men (7.5%). The prevalence of Malaria in Kaduna State with respect to age range showed that age range less than twenty years (< 20) years recorded more malaria cases than the other age groups. A single factor statistical analysis of variance performed on table one showed that the test result for the five years together was statistically significant, since the P value was less than the alpha which was 0.05. Therefore the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted, which stated that they early reported malaria cases in four different towns in Kaduna State for five years was significant.

Key words: Prevalence, Malaria, Retrospective, Variance, Hypothesis, Virulent, Plasmodium falciparum.

INTRODUCTION

Malaria is a mosquito borne infectious disease of human and animals caused by the genus Plasmodium. Five species of Plasmodium have been reported to be infectious, and can be transmitted by insects. The vast

majority of deaths are caused by Plasmodium falciparum while Plasmodium vivax, Plasmodium ovale, and Plasmodium malariae cause a generally milder form of malaria that is not fatal. The zoonotic species, P. knowlesi prevalent in South East Asia causes malaria in

macaques, but can also cause severe infection in humans (Nayyer et al., 2002).

Malaria has been documented to affect 3.3 billion people, or half of the world's population, in 106 countries and territories according to WHO - NMFS, (2010). World Health Organization (2011), estimated that 216 million cases of malaria occurred in 2010, and 81% were in the African region. WHO World malaria fact sheet (2012), reported that there were 655,000 malaria deaths in 2010, 91% in the African Region, and 86% were children under five years of age. Malaria has been reported to be the third leading cause of death for children below five years worldwide, after Pneumonia and Diarrheal disease. Most deaths occur among children living in Africa where a child dies every minute of malaria and the disease accounts for approximately 22% of all childhood deaths (WHO - WMFS, 2012). In 2017, there was an estimated 219 million cases of malaria in 87 countries. The estimated number of malaria deaths stood at 435 000 in 2017 (WHO, 2019). The African region reportedly carries a high share of the global malaria burden (WHO, 2019). In 2017, the region was home to 92% of malaria cases and 93% of malaria deaths (WHO, 2019). Thirty countries in Sub-Saharan Africa

account for 90% of global malaria deaths (WHO, 2012). Nigeria, Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), Ethiopia, and Uganda account for nearly 50% of the global malaria deaths (WHO, 2012).

Malaria has also been reported to be the second leading cause of death from infectious diseases in Africa, after HIV/AIDS: Almost one out of five deaths of children less than five years in Africa is due to malaria (NMFS, 2010). Malaria is known to be a major public health problem in Nigeria where it accounts for more cases of deaths than any other country in the world. Malaria is a risk for 97% of Nigeria's population. The remaining 3% of the population live in the malaria free highlands (NMFS, 2010). There are an estimated 100 million malaria cases with over 300,000 deaths per year in Nigeria. This compares with 215,000 deaths per year in Nigeria from HIV/AIDS. Malaria contributes to an estimated 11% of maternal mortality. Malaria has been reported to accounts for 60% of outpatient visits and 30% of hospitalizations among children under five years of age in Nigeria (NMFS, 2010). Malaria has the greatest prevalence, close to 50%, in children age 6-59 months in the South West,

North Central, and North West regions (Peterson et al., 2011). Malaria has the least prevalence, 27.6 percent, in children age 6 to 59 months in the South East region (NMFS, 2010).

This research was designed to study the prevalence, of resistant *Plasmodium falciparum* from Kafanchan, Kachia, Kaduna, and Zaria towns in Kaduna State Nigeria.

The objectives of the study are as follows:

1. Determination of reported patients from Kafanchan, Kachia, Kaduna and Zaria, Kaduna State Nigeria (2013 to 2017).
2. Determination of reported Malaria patients profile from four towns in Kaduna State (2013 – 2017).
3. Prevalence of Malaria in Kaduna State Nigeria (2013 to 2017).
4. Prevalence of Malaria in Kaduna State with respect to age range (2013 to 2017).
5. Prevalence of Malaria in Kaduna State Nigeria with respect to gender (2013 to 2017).

Methods

Retrospective Study

Review of Medical Records

Retrospective study was carried out

by reviewing the medical records of patients from the period of July 2013 to July 2017, to determine the number of patients that reported to the various health facilities. The medical records of reported malaria cases from four health centers in Kaduna State were collated from medical records office of the health centers studied for the following years: 2013, 2014, 2015, 2016, and 2017.

Ethical Approval

Ethical approval for the research was obtained from ethical committee of the Kaduna State Ministry of Health. Patient's anonymity was maintained, and the findings were treated with utmost confidentiality.

The Study Design

The basic parameter considered were

- (a) No of reported patients.
- (b) Number of reported Malaria cases.
- (c) The age group of Malaria cases.

The age of the patients were grouped according to WHO (2013).

- (d) Gender (male/ female) of patients.

Patients hospital records of both male and female patients attending general hospitals from four different towns (Kaduna, Kafanchan, Kachia and Zaria) in Kaduna State. Their ages ranged from two years to forty

years and above, of those who reported to the different hospitals with history of fever.

Method of Analysis

Statistical analysis was used to analyze the results obtained

Study Sites

General Hospital Sabo, Kaduna. General Hospital kafanchan, Kaduna State. General Hospital kachia, Kaduna State. Major Mohammed B Memorial Hospital, Zaria.

Study Area

Kaduna State is in north central Nigeria. Kaduna State has interstate boundaries with Niger state to the west, Zamfara, Kastina and Kano state to the North, Bauchi and Plateau state to the East and FCT Abuja and Nassarawa State to the South.

Its capital is Kaduna. The main cities and towns are Kaduna (capital city), Zaria, Kagoro, Kafanchan, Kachia and Zonkwa. The vegetation characteristic is that of guinea savanna with scattered trees and shrub.

Kaduna state lies at a location with coordinates of $10^{\circ}37'64''\text{N}$, $7^{\circ}7'095''\text{E}$ with Latitude 10.609319 and Longitude 7.429504 . Kaduna is a commercial center (www.latlong.net). The population of Kaduna State as at 2020 is 1,113,000 (www.macrotrends.net). The weather is 23°C , wind South-West at

13km/h , 90% humidity and covers an area of 45,711.2 square kilometers. The main ethnic groups in Kaduna State are the Gbagi, Hausa, Kadara, Kamuku and Kurama. Fifty-seven languages are spoken in the states; of these, Gbari and Hausa are the major ones. Sabo Tasha lies in Kaduna south with latitude 10.4619, and longitude 7.42722. Kafanchan is a town in South Kaduna state in north-central Nigeria. It is a location of a junction station of the Nigerian Railway Corporation, and sits on the line connecting Port Harcourt, Enugu, Kuru, Bauchi and finally Maiduguri. The map of Kaduna State showing all the towns is seen in (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Map of Kaduna State

Results and Discussion

Prevalence of Malaria

The total reported Patient attendance (%) from four towns in Kaduna State from 2013 to 2017 was shown to be one hundred and fifty six thousand and fifty three (156053) (Figure 2 attachment 2). The mean patient attendance from four towns in Kaduna State from 2013 to 2017 was 26009. The total number of reported malaria Patients attendance from four different hospitals in Kaduna State Nigeria (2013 to 2017) is thirty four thousand, one hundred and twenty one (34,121) (Figure2, attachment 2, and figure 3, attachment 3). The percentage prevalence of Malaria in Kaduna State from the four health facilities in these towns (Kaduna, Kafanchan, Kachia, Zaria), from 2013 to 2017 was 21.87%.

The malaria prevalence rate (21.87%) was higher than (7.5%) recorded by Garba *et al.*, (2016). The higher prevalence could be as a result of economic factors. WHO (2005) had recommended the use of ACT as the front line antimalarial drug for the treatment of malaria. However the prices of these ACT drugs has gone high in Nigeria almost beyond the reach of the average Nigerian.

Figure 2: Total reported Patients (%) from four Towns in Kaduna State (2013-2017)

The yearly reported malaria cases showed that Kafanchan and Kachia towns had the highest prevalence rate of 28.22% and 28.39% respectively (attached Table 1) and (attached Figure 4).

Figure 4: Yearly reported Malaria cases (%) from four towns in Kaduna State (2013 – 2017)

The higher prevalence of malaria seen in the southern senatorial towns agrees with the work of Garba *et al.*, (2016) who opined that the reason was due to higher rainfall of 1530mm. The prevalence of malaria here significantly correlates with rainfall. Rainfall provides sufficient breeding sites and relevant humidity enhancing reproduction and survival of adult mosquitoes (Nacher, *et al.*, 2001). A single factor statistical analysis of variance performed on Table one above showed that the test result for the five years together was statistically significant, since

the P value was less than the alpha which was 0.05. Therefore the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted, which stated that they early reported malaria cases from four different towns in Kaduna State for five years was significant.

The prevalence of Malaria in Kaduna State with respect to age range showed that age range less than twenty years (<20) years recorded more malaria cases than the other age groups (see attached Figure 5).

Figure 5: Total reported Malaria cases (%) with respect to age range

This result agrees with the findings of Umaru and Uyaiabasi, (2015) and Inabo and Umaru, (2011). This supports the assertion that younger ones are more disposed to malaria infection in sub Saharan Africa. These could be due to the fact that these young ones have lower immunity against malaria.

The result of prevalence of malaria with respect to gender showed that more female (56.22%), than men (43.78%) with Malaria infection from four towns in Kaduna State reported to the health facilities in Kaduna State (2013 – 2017).

This is also consistent with the assertion that females are more vulnerable to this disease in Africa. This higher prevalence rate observed

in females agrees with the work of many researchers (Otajevwo, 2013, Okonkwo *et al.*, 2012, and Alli *et al.*, 2013). The reason for higher prevalence among females may be a reflection of differences in reporting.

There appears to be no scientific evidence linking malaria prevalence to gender.

Evidence from some countries indicates that restricted mobility of women may also impede their attendance at primary health care clinics for malaria testing, thereby increasing their risk of infection (Garba *et al.*, 2016).

Figure 6: Prevalence of Malaria (%) in Relation to gender from four Towns in Kaduna State (2013 – 2017).

Summary and Conclusion

The total reported Patient attendance (%) from four towns in Kaduna State from 2013 to 2017 was shown to be one hundred and fifty six thousand and fifty three (156053) (Figure 2).

The total number of reported Malaria Patients attendance from four different hospitals in Kaduna State Nigeria (2013 to 2017) is thirty four

thousand, one hundred and twenty one (34,121) (Figure 2 and figure 3).

The prevalence of Malaria in Kaduna State with respect to age range showed that age group less than twenty years (20) and below recorded more malaria cases than the other age groups (Figure 4).

- The prevalence of Malaria in Kaduna State with respect to gender, showed that females recorded more malaria cases than the male.

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